

LIGAND-BASED DRUG DESIGN STUDIES ON SOME SELECTED CHEMICAL ACTIVATORS OF APOPTOSIS REGULATOR (BCL-2) FOR CANCEROUS CELL INHIBITION

David Ebuka Arthur^{1*}, Lawan Bukar Inuwa¹, Karimatu Abdullahi², Benjamin O. Elegbe²

¹Department of Pure and Applied Chemistry, Faculty of Physical Chemistry, University of Maiduguri, Maiduguri, Borno State

²Department of Chemistry, Baze University Abuja, Nigeria

Corresponding Author's Email Address: eadavid@unimaid.edu.ng

Tel: +2348039183847

ABSTRACT

In spite of the substantial increase in the study of cancer treatment over the past decades, the disease is still a serious global health challenge and poses a considerable study. B-cell lymphoma 2 (BCL-2) apoptosis regulators were identified as potential targets in eliminating cancer cells, due to their high affinity for Bcl-2 Associated X-protein (BAX protein) which functions as a tool for bringing death to any cell. Hence, developing new BCL-2 activators with better therapeutic effect is strongly needed. In an attempt to overcome this challenge, this research is aimed at developing a mathematical model that can be used in designing novel potent chemical moieties with better BCL-2 apoptosis regulator via prediction of their activities using a newly developed Quantitative structure activity relationship (QSAR) model. The material in the study includes the chemical dataset collected from pubmed, while the methods used are the standard QSAR development method as stated in the Setubal records. The main program used in the study is the QSARIN. The QSAR model developed in the study was presented as $pEC50 = -0.0148(ALogP) - 0.0043(nO) + 0.0144(nHBint8) - 0.6533(ETA_dEpsilon_B) + 5.2861$. The model was selected for its effective use in predicting novel chemical compounds or test set found within the applicability domain of the model because it has the best statistical parameters such as: coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.7836$), cross validation coefficient ($Q^2_{loo} = 0.7094$), and adjusted R^2 ($R^2_{adj} = 0.7475$). The models was able to predict the activity of the compounds used in developing the models, the validation statistical parameter for the test set were not as significant as that for the training set, but the result suggest that the model can be improved upon by applying other nonlinear modeling techniques like that of machine learning algorithm and support vector machine or by replacing the molecules identified as outliers and influential molecules in the data set with other molecules of similar structure.

Keywords: Cancer, QSAR, BCL-2, Density functional theory, QSARIN.

INTRODUCTION

The BCL-2 family proteins are central regulators of the mitochondrion-mediated apoptotic cell death. They are characterized by containing up to four conserved stretches of amino acids, known as BCL-2 homology (BH) domains (1, 2). They are usually grouped into three distinct subclasses. One subclass is composed of BAX and BAK that mediate apoptosis by triggering destabilization of the outer mitochondrial membrane (OMM) and consequently releasing the apoptogenic factors, such as cytochrome c, from mitochondria to the cytosol (3, 4). The activation of BAX/BAK is suppressed by the remaining subclass composed of BCL-2, BCL-XL, BCL-w, MCL-1, A1 and BCL-B, all of which contain the four BH domains. The interplay between the three subclasses of the BCL-2 family determines the fate of cells in response to developmental or stress signals (5).

This paper provides a novel approach to treating cancerous cells, as well as providing a safe, effective way of targeting specific cells. The BCL-2 molecule targets cancerous cells and triggers an apoptotic cascade in them, leading to their death. The use of the BCL-2 molecule is a valuable tool in cancer research, as it has been shown to selectively inhibit the survival of cancerous cells while maintaining the functionality of healthy cells. The benefits of using the BCL-2 molecule are vast, and its potential to help further advance cancer research is invaluable. Overall, this product is an excellent solution to target cancerous cells and promote selective inhibition of their growth, making it a great tool for cancer research.

Computer-Aided Drug Design (CADD) is a potent technique in the design of possible drugs for inhibition of cancer cells (6). This strong tool has been playing a vital part in applicability domain detection, which greatly improves on the identification of molecule fragments or descriptors that can improve the activities of the compounds in progress cycles in drug study. The goal of this investigation is to create a QSAR model that will forecast the activity of some compounds as an effective BCL-2 apoptosis regulator activator.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research was performed on HP laptop furnished with a dual-core Intel (R) PENTIUM (R) B940 CPU processor running at 2.0 GHz and 4.0 GB of RAM running on Windows 8. The following softwares were used in this research: Chemdraw 19.1, SPARTAN "14 v 1.1.0, PaDEL, QSARINS.

Chemical data set retrieval and activity pre-processing

36 compounds with their corresponding biological activities against Apoptosis Regulator BCL-2 were retrieved from Pubchem NMMLSC (<http://www.bindingdb.org/>). The biological activities (in nM) were transformed by taking the negative logarithm to base 10 (eqn 1). Chemical structures of the data set with their corresponding experimental pEC₅₀ are expressed in Table 1.

$$pEC_{50} = -\log_{10}(EC_{50} \times 10^{-9}) \dots\dots\dots 1$$

2-D drawings of the compounds and geometry optimization

2-dimensional structures of the compounds were drawn using Perkin-Elmer ChemDraw software and then converted to 3-dimensional format by using Spartan 14.0 software program. Geometry optimization of the analogues was carried out on the Spartan 14.0 interface by

employing Density functional theory calculation with B3LYP/6-311G* basis set. 2D structures of all the compounds were presented in Table 1.

Calculation of Molecular Descriptors

The optimized structures in sdf format were imported to pharmaceutical data exploratory (PADEL) software package to compute the molecular descriptors that are responsible for the biological activities of the analogues (7).

Data Division

The result obtained from PADEL in excel worksheet was pre-treated using Kennard-Stone data pre-treatment software to eliminate redundant and non-relevant descriptors. Data division software was then utilized to partition the data set into training and test set (8).

Normalization and Data Division

Normalization was carried out on the calculated descriptors using the expression (eq2) in order to get a good and robust model.

$$Y = \frac{Y_i - Y_{min}}{Y_{max} - Y_{min}} \text{-----}2$$

Where Y_i is the descriptor's value for each molecule, Y_{min} and Y_{max} are minimum and maximum value for each descriptor respectively. In order to remove redundant data, pre-treatment was carried out on the normalized data using the software obtained from dtclab.webs.com/software-tools. Also, the treatment data were separated into 70% training set and 30% test set (Prediction set) by dtclab.webs.com/software-tools by engaging Kennard and Stone's algorithm. This algorithms have been reported by several QSAR articles like (9).

Applicability Domain (APD) of the Built Model

The APD of a model can be defined as "the response and chemical structure space in which the model makes predictions with a given reliability(10). The aim of APD is to define a hypothetical space in which a model can make dependable forecasts. The leverage approach was utilized to describing chemical compound h_i , and expressions (3) describe it:

$$h_i = Y_i (Y^T Y)^{-1} Y_i^T \quad (3)$$

where Y_i is the training compound matrix of i . Y is the $a \times b$ descriptor matrix of the training set compound and Y^T is the transpose matrix of Y utilized to size the model. The warning leverage (h^*) that is, a predictive tool is the limit of normal values for Y outliers and is defined as follows:

$$h^* = 3 \frac{(j+1)}{m} \quad (4)$$

Where j and m are the training set compounds and the molecular properties respectively.

RESULTS

Table 1 showed the predicted endpoint values and their corresponding structures, which were previously mentioned in the writeup. Meanwhile, the features of the built model are presented in Table 2.

Tables 1 is basically molecular structure of the compounds and their activities, while table 2 in details shows the validation parameters to confirm the model built with QSARIN program (11, 12). Table 2 also shows the external validation parameters, interconnection and statistical examination for descriptor used in the QSAR model, while table 3 shows the definition of the descriptors used in the model.

Table1: Structures and Zinc identification number (ZincID) of the Chemical dataset along with their experimentally and predicted endpoints in pEC₅₀

Name	Structures	Status	Exp. Endpoint (pEC ₅₀)	Pred. Endpoint (pEC ₅₀)	Residual	Zinc ID of Ligand
AP1		Training	5.2582	5.241	-0.0172	ZINC38145472
AP2		Training	5.172	5.1867	0.0146	ZINC07089644
AP3		Training	5.2734	5.2763	0.0028	ZINC19802256
AP4		Training	5.2406	5.2569	0.0162	ZINC08830252
AP5		Training	5.1901	5.1898	-0.0002	ZINC00707827
AP6		Training	5.232	5.2197	-0.0124	ZINC25326362

AP7		Prediction	5.1817	5.2435	0.0617	ZINC13122352
AP8		Prediction	5.1894	5.22	0.0306	ZINC00359743
AP9		Training	5.1657	5.1797	0.014	ZINC11363994
AP10		Prediction	5.2072	5.2385	0.0313	ZINC13126047
AP11		Training	5.2225	5.2203	-0.0022	ZINC03998376
AP12		Training	5.2013	5.2093	0.008	ZINC13571887
AP13		Prediction	5.1719	5.1899	0.018	ZINC00310678
AP14		Training	5.1874	5.2078	0.0204	ZINC00310112
AP15		Training	5.1867	5.1963	0.0096	

AP16		Prediction	5.2208	5.2244	0.0036	ZINC00265971
AP17		Training	5.1705	5.1698	-0.0006	ZINC12428973
AP18		Training	5.2681	5.2613	-0.0068	ZINC03880366
AP19		Training	5.2761	5.2816	0.0055	ZINC15953262
AP20		Training	5.2047	5.2049	0.0001	ZINC13139536
AP21		Training	5.2158	5.2098	-0.0061	ZINC01627076
AP22		Training	5.2264	5.1966	-0.0298	ZINC60238766
AP23		Training	5.2004	5.218	0.0177	ZINC02633911
AP24		Training	5.1945	5.2027	0.0081	ZINC00342883

AP25		Training	5.2605	5.2603	-0.0002	ZINC00051313
AP26		Training	5.2425	5.2262	-0.0163	ZINC02951107
AP27		Training	5.2101	5.2173	0.0071	ZINC08667024
AP28		Training	5.1943	5.1907	-0.0037	ZINC08672153
AP29		Training	5.1755	5.1845	0.009	ZINC08656557
AP30		Training	5.2032	5.2173	0.0141	ZINC01161125
AP31		Training	5.2327	5.2087	-0.024	ZINC00532766
AP32		Training	5.2331	5.2204	-0.0127	ZINC13685591
AP33		Training	5.2559	5.218	-0.0378	ZINC02633911

AP34		Prediction	5.2502	5.2131	-0.0371	ZINC12695462
AP35		Prediction	5.2641	5.1777	-0.0864	ZINC15989487
AP36		Training	5.2228	5.2454	0.0226	ZINC09319034

The results were further specified in plots to illuminate further the statistical data presented in table 2, with respect the validity of the model created to predict the effective concentrations of small chemical compounds on the apoptosis regulator BCL-2.

Figures 1 to 4 are graph of predicted activity against observed activity, plot of residual versus predicted activity, William's graph, and insurbia plot respectively.

$$pEC_{50} = -0.0148(\mathbf{A}Log\mathbf{P}) - 0.0043(\mathbf{nO}) + 0.0144(\mathbf{nHBint8}) - 0.6533(\mathbf{ETA_dEpsilon_B}) + 5.2861$$

Table 2: Features of built model, descriptive statistics, descriptors and their coefficients in the model

Variable	Coeff	Std. coeff.	Std. err.	(+/-) Co. int. 95%	p-value
Intercept	5.2861		0.0135	0.0278	0
A Log P	-0.0148	-0.5135	0.003	0.0061	0
nO	-0.0043	-0.249	0.0019	0.0039	0.0297
nHBint8	0.0144	0.4955	0.0031	0.0063	0.0001
ETA_dEpsilon_B	-0.6533	-0.4461	0.1457	0.3008	0.0001
(Fitting criteria)					
R ² : 0.7836	R ² _{adj} : 0.7475		R ² -R ² _{adj} : 0.0361		LOF: 0.0004
RMSE tr: 0.0148	MAE tr: 0.0117		CCC _{tr} : 0.8787		F: 21.7260
(Internal validation criteria)					
Q ² ₁₀₀ : 0.7094	R ² -Q ² ₁₀₀ : 0.0742		RMSE cv: 0.0172		MAE cv: 0.0138
CCC _{cv} : 0.8394					
Coeff = Coefficient; Std. coeff. = standard coefficient; Std. err. = standard error					

Table 3: Specified Definitions of Descriptors

S/NO	Descriptors	Definition	Class
1	ALogP	Ghose-Crippen LogK _{ow}	2D
2	nO	Number of oxygen atoms	2D
3	nHBint8	Count of E-State descriptors of strength for potential Hydrogen Bonds of path length 8	2D
4	ETA_dEpsilon_B	A measure of contribution of unsaturation	2D

Figure 1: A plot of pEC50 predicted by the model vs the experimental pEC50 (endpoint)

Figure 2: A plot of residual values from the difference between the predicted and experimental pEC₅₀ against the values of the predicted endpoints in pEC₅₀

Figure 3: Williams plot of the standardized residuals of the dataset evaluated values against their evaluated descriptor-based leverage values

Figure 4: Isurbia plot of predicted endpoint (pEC_{50}) values against leverage values

Discussion

QSAR was used to examine the structure activity relationship (SAR) of the some compounds as an effective BCL-2 activators. The quality of a model in a QSAR study is conveyed by its predictive and forecast capacities. Hence the software (Kennard-Stone algorithm) was employed to generate a test set that is a noble replication of the training set. The predictive, strength, dependability capability of the established model were assessed by inside and outside endorsement factors. Tables 2 shows the statistical principles for the QSAR model (11, 12).

The null hypothesis at the 95% confidence limit of the built model at $p > 0.05$, indicates that an unresolved relationship does not exist between the activities of the activator molecules and the molecular properties utilized in constructing the model. This indicates that the null hypothesis is disallowed. Therefore, we propose the alternative hypothesis. Henceforth, we concluded that the molecular properties used in building the model at $p < 0.05$ (13, 14) is responsible for the activity of the molecule as well as their mechanism of action in active site.

Table 2 shows the coefficient of the descriptors and coefficient of determinant (R^2) of 0.7836 > 0.5 which is the minimum value described by Roy and Tropsha (12, 15, 16), implies that the coefficient is in agreement with the built model.

Figures 1 and 2 display the graphical illustration and level of correlations between the calculated activities against observed activities and calculated activities against residual values. The $R^2 = 0.7836$ for the overall dataset means that there is a high correlation between the observed endpoint and predicted or calculated endpoint, which is also in line with the recognized QSAR boundary values described in Table 2. Figure 3 demonstrates the

computational capability and correctness because the standardized residual values for the datasets fall within ± 2.5 (17-20).

The Williams and insurbia plot shown in Figure 3 and 4 respectively, suggest that all the molecules with the exception of AP35 and AP7 which are shown to be inside the applicability domain of the model. The leverage values of some compounds were observed to be < 0.517 which is the warning leverage (h^*). Compound AP7 is an influential molecule since the leverage value was found to be more than the warning leverage. Compound AP7 and AP35 are both outliers, since the model was unable to predict the activity of these compounds. In addition, it is also observed that all the compounds were within the defined space of ± 2.5 standard residual values which point out that only compound AP35 and AP7 compound is said to be outliers.

Conclusions

The building of the QSAR model has been the unbiased beyond the collection, optimization, and modelling of some selected compounds as agents against BCL-2 apoptosis regulator. A model was built with brilliant statistical parameters; $R^2 = 0.7836$, $R^2_{adj} = 0.7475$, $Q^2_{loo} = 0.7094$, LOF = 0.0004, MAE cv: 0.0138 and $CCC_{cv} = 0.8394$. The model was successfully used to predict the activity of the test set compounds within an acceptable minimal range of statistical error. This suggest that the model can be used to design or at least predict the activity of other compounds with similar chemical features in this case.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Adams JM, & Cory S. Life-or-Death Decisions by the Bcl-2 Protein Family. *Trends in Biochemical Sciences*. 2001;26(1), 61-66.
- [2]. Opferman JT, & Korsmeyer SJ. Apoptosis in the Development and Maintenance of the Immune System. *Nature Immunology*, 2003;4(5), 410-415.
- [3]. Antignani A, & Youle RJ. How do Bax and Bak Lead to Permeabilization of the Outer Mitochondrial Membrane? *Current Opinion in Cell Biology*, 2006: 18(6), 685-689.
- [4]. Green DR, & Kroemer G. The Pathophysiology of Mitochondrial Cell Death. *Science*. 2004;305(5684), 626-629.
- [5]. Ku B, Liang C, Jung JU, & Oh B-H. Evidence that Inhibition of BAX Activation by BCL-2 Involves its Tight and Preferential Interaction with the BH3 Domain of BAX. *Cell Research*, 2011;21(4):627-641.
- [6]. Kubinyi H. QSAR and 3D QSAR in Drug Design Part 1: Methodology. *Drug Discovery Today*. 1997;2(11), 457-467.
- [7]. Yap CW. PaDEL-descriptor: An Open Source Software to Calculate Molecular Descriptors and Fingerprints. *Journal of Computational Chemistry*, 2011;32(7),1466-1474.
- [8]. De P, Kar S, Ambure P, & Roy K. Prediction Reliability of QSAR Models: An Overview of Various Validation Tools. *Archives of Toxicology*, 2022;96(5):1279-1295.
- [9]. Khaled K, & Abdel-Shafi N. Quantitative Structure and Activity Relationship modeling Study of Corrosion Inhibitors: Genetic Function Approximation and Molecular Dynamics Simulation Methods. *International Journal of Electrochemical Science*, 2011;6, 4077-94.

-
- [10]. Ambure P, Aher RB, Gajewicz A, Puzyn T, & Roy K. “NanoBRIDGES” Software: Open Access Tools to Perform QSAR and Nano-QSAR Modeling. *Chemometrics and Intelligent Laboratory Systems*, 2015:147, 1-13.
- [11]. Gramatica P. Principles of QSAR Models Validation: Internal and External. *QSAR & Combinatorial Science*, 2007:26(5), 694-701.
- [12]. Tropsha A. Best practices for QSAR model development, validation, and exploitation. *Molecular Informatics*, 2010:29(6-7), 476-488.
- [13]. Roy K, & Mitra I. On Various Metrics used for Validation of Predictive QSAR Models with Applications in Virtual Screening and Focused Library Design. *Combinatorial Chemistry & High Throughput Screening*, 2011:14(6), 450-474.
- [14]. Veerasamy R, Rajak H, Jain A, Sivadasan S, Varghese CP, & Agrawal RK. Validation of QSAR Models-Strategies and Importance. *International Journal of Drug Discovery*, 2011:3, 511-519.
- [15]. Roy K. Advances in QSAR modeling. Applications in Pharmaceutical, Chemical, Food, Agricultural and Environmental Sciences; Springer: Cham, Switzerland. 2017:555, 39.
- [16]. Roy K, & Narayan Das R. A Review on Principles, Theory and Practices of 2D-QSAR. *Current Drug Metabolism*, 2014:15(4), 346-379.
- [17]. Arthur DE, Ameenu Y, Peter FM, Aroh A, & Arthur CC. An Assessment to Determine the Level of Some Selected Heavy Metals in Rice (*Oryza sativa*) Consumed Within Funtua Metropolis. *Chemical Review and Letters*, 2021;4(3):164-170.
- [18]. Arthur DE, Ejeh S, & Uzairu A. Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship (QSAR) and Design of Novel Ligands that Demonstrate High Potency and Target Selectivity as Protein Tyrosine Phosphatase 1B (PTP 1B) Inhibitors as an Effective Strategy used to Model Anti-Diabetic Agents. *Journal of Receptors and Signal Transduction*, 2020:40(6), 501-520.
- [19]. Arthur DE, Elegbe BO, Aroh AO, Soliman M. Computational Drug Design of Novel COVID-19 Inhibitor. *Bulletin of the National Research Centre*, 2022:46(1), 1-29.
- [20]. Arthur DE, & Uzairu A. Molecular Docking Studies on the Interaction of NCI Anticancer Analogues with Human Phosphatidylinositol 4, 5-Bisphosphate 3-Kinase Catalytic Subunit. *Journal of King Saud University-Science*, 2019:31(4), 1151-1166.